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DIDACTIC CONCEPT OF E-LEARNING

Abstract. E-learning is one of the priority directions of the educational system in Georgia and is defined in the education law on higher education. When implementing the e-learning format, teaching productivity increases. The student / pupil, who acquires education through innovative methodology, develops more general-transferable skills, therefore quickly adapts and self-affirms in society.

Keywords: student, didactics, e-learning, process, concept

Анотація. Електронне навчання є одним із пріоритетних напрямів розвитку системи освіти в Грузії та визначено у Законах «Про освіту» та «Про вищу освіту». У разі впровадження формату електронного навчання підвищується продуктивність навчання. Учень, який здобуває освіту за інноваційною методикою, виробляє більш загальнопереносні навички, тому швидше адаптується і самостверджується в суспільстві.

Ключові слова: студент, дидактика, електронне навчання, процес, концепція

We are members of the e-learning project and have received permission to use the materials offered by them and processed by us in e-learning, we have tried to create a didactic concept of e-learning, which represents the way of e-learning in a systematic way and will help all interested persons in implementing the e-learning course.

We presented it in a revised form to the Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation and earned quite a high score.

E-learning is one of the main challenges of XXI century among innovative teaching methodologies and at the same time, the way of solving the following problems:

- Courses/Education are available for students in the region and at the same time equal opportunity for people to get high quality education on the spot;
- There is a real chance for the lecturer/teacher to raise their professionalism in the continuous education mode.

E-learning is successfully implemented in foreign universities. As European and American experience has shown, the electronic format of teaching, in general, is an effective and useful tool for innovative teaching, effectively equipping students with sectoral and general-transferable skills, and increasing the awareness of universities through which it is possible:

Access to quality, up-to-date information for all stakeholders;

- ✓ Increasing awareness and rebranding of the University;
- ✓ Overview deepening international relations;
- ✓ Overview increasing the number of students;
- ✓ Advanced experience sharing-implementation;
- ✓ Creation and introduction of innovative technologies and relevant, author's, didactic methodologies in teaching.

In addition, students have more opportunities to:

- Adapt the training to your own individual requirements;
- The learner can control the learning process himself;
- To adapt the study material individually and make it more effective for the study;
- Re-revise the material;

In the implementation of the e-learning format, the productivity of teaching increases, which is expressed in:

Overview in enhancing student competence;

- In the dynamics of mastering new technologies;
- In ensuring effective teamwork;
- activities of multiple recurrence capabilities through the process of learning the current error reduction.

The lecturer himself has the opportunity to conduct the teaching in such a format:

- ✓ Ensure effective distribution and utilization of learning resources;
- ✓ Focus on quality (ability to re-review and edit material);
- ✓ Easily evaluate the results obtained;
- ✓ Have more feedback and feedback with the student even when he is not in the audience;
- ✓ Share knowledge on a global scale, which can serve as the basis for creating new, author's knowledge in teaching methodology;
- ✓ He / she works with Target groups, using specific activities different from the traditional learning process (conversation-chat, e-mail, Voice IP, Video over IP, resources HTML-content-PDF, Wiki) and thus making teaching-learning results more effective;
- ✓ The student / pupil, who acquires education through innovative methodology, develops more general-transferable skills, therefore quickly adapts and self-affirms in society.

E-learning is one of the priority directions of the educational system in Georgia and is defined in the education law on higher education; however, it is only now gaining ground in

educational institutions, especially in the regions, and naturally, much needs to be established and improved. Sharing the experience of European and American universities is a very useful work and several projects for the introduction of e-education have been implemented for several pilot universities throughout Georgia. The advantage of this innovation in teaching over the traditional learning environment is beyond doubt, however, adjusting it to Georgian reality and replacing the existing environment with a certain dose requires a lot of effort and work. As the analysis of the educational policy of universities (regional) has shown, there are no systematic approaches to e-learning as an innovation, an alternative (not an exclusion) to the traditional learning environment; Its implementation, even in the form of separate courses, with the exception of single, initiating.

The creation of the system model of e-learning as an innovative format in the context of the above discussion envisages: formation of systematic approaches for the creation and establishment of interactive teaching materials enriched with multi-media means for students/pupils.

It can be implemented by providing continuous education for lecturers. This process will be focused on the involvement of modern information technologies in the educational process, research and implementation of software and methodological tools for its implementation.

To implement the goal, the following tasks must be solved:

He / she will coordinate the retraining of university lecturers for the creation of electronic courses, preparation of future (or current) school teachers, or retraining for the implementation of electronic education. To implement this, all stages of the process of developing and delivering e-learning courses must be fully considered: planning, creation, piloting, implementation and evaluation;

Coordinate and manage the progress of the e-learning project, develop its respective methodological and didactic concepts, process the teaching material, give it an electronic form, support the trainees in the learning process, ensure the administration of infrastructure and its functioning, ensure the proper functioning of teaching management systems and other infrastructure elements, develop a tutoring model, develop training modules in these directions and.

From the didactic point of view, special attention is paid to the study of the role and functions of the mentor in the process of e-learning, about which there are no unified approaches in Georgia (the model itself is not implemented in Georgian universities).

At this point, it can only be said that its function is completely different from that of an advisor. The creation of didactic methodology of e-learning is also an innovation for Georgian reality. This is a common work of a wide range of specialists (teacher, Methodist, psychologist, IT specialist), without reconciling data and creating a common product, we cannot speak about unified standards of e-learning.

References

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